

Local Government in Canada

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Martin Horak

Department of Political Science
Western University

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw

University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Canada is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

Western University: Martin Horak
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

David Mark/Pixabay

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Canada: An Introduction.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Canada: An Introduction	11
2.2. <i>Governing the Construction of Transit Infrastructure in Toronto and Vancouver</i>	15
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Canada: An Introduction.....	20
3.2. <i>Property Tax Reliance and the Re-Emergence of Provincial Funding Transfers to Local Government in Ontario</i>	22
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Canada: An Introduction	27
4.2. <i>Beyond Municipal Amalgamations in Ontario</i>	29
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Canada: An Introduction.....	34
5.2. <i>Representing Toronto’s Distinct Interests to the Ontario Provincial Government</i>	36
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Canada: An Introduction	40
6.2. <i>Adopting Ranked-Choice Voting in London, Ontario</i>	43

Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Canada: An Introduction

Martin Horak, *Department of Political Science, Western University*

Since provincial governments have constitutional responsibility over local government in Canada, the primary nexus of intergovernmental relations is the provincial-municipal one. Federal government involvement in local affairs has been episodic, and has been largely limited to the development of various infrastructure funding transfers, which usually require matching funding across all three levels of government. The Federation of Canadian Municipalities (FCM) represents and lobbies for municipal interests at the federal level; however, given the lack of institutionalized federal-local relations, place-specific and project-specific advocacy by local political representatives and/or local members of federal Parliament also play a role in shaping flows of federal funding for local infrastructure. Over the last 20 years, the growth of federal cost-shared infrastructure funding, as well as the rise of some project-specific efforts at federal-provincial-municipal coordination, have deepened and broadened multilevel governance mechanisms spanning all three levels of government; yet tri-level coordination is still partial, unstable, and highly vulnerable to short-term political pressures.⁶⁵

Systems of provincial-municipal intergovernmental relations vary significantly from province to province. However, in most provinces they are shaped by a combination of factors that is arguably unique to Canada: 1. Comprehensive provincial legal authority over local governments; 2. High reliance of local governments on locally raised revenues;⁶⁶ 3. Low intergovernmental political integration; 4. Low intergovernmental administrative integration. The latter two points deserve some elaboration. With respect to political integration, in most of Canada, local government is non-partisan; and in the places where it is partisan (Vancouver, and many Quebec municipalities), local parties are often different than provincial parties. As a result, in the political sphere intergovernmental relations tend to lack the glue of integrated party systems that exist in many other countries. With respect to administrative integration, Canada has no unified civil service that operates across levels of government. Each province has its own civil service system; and there is no comprehensive civil service system for local governments. This makes intergovernmental communication on the administrative front more difficult and less systematic than it otherwise might be.

Provincial-municipal relations have evolved differently in different provinces in response to these realities. In British Columbia, for example, the provincial government in the 1970s instituted a system of ‘regional districts’ – large-scale service-sharing structures that also serve

⁶⁵ For a detailed discussion, see Martin Horak, ‘Conclusion: Understanding Multilevel Governance in Canada’s Cities’ in Martin Horak and Robert Young (eds), *Sites of Governance: Multilevel Governance and Policy Making in Canada’s Big Cities* (University of Toronto Press 2012).

⁶⁶ See report section 3 on local finances for further discussion.

as intermediary institutions between the province and municipalities, supporting a relatively consensual model of provincial-municipal relations. In Ontario, by contrast, the norm is much more one of provincial legislative and regulatory dominance of local governments, with limited openness to local concerns. In this context, provincial-level associations of municipalities have become important intermediaries in the provincial-municipal relationship.⁶⁷

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Côté A and Fenn M, *Provincial-Municipal Relations in Ontario: Approaching an Inflection Point* (Institute on Municipal Finance and Governance 2014)

Martin H, 'Conclusion: Understanding Multilevel Governance in Canada's Cities' in Martin Horak and Robert Young (eds), *Sites of Governance: Multilevel Governance and Policy Making in Canada's Big Cities* (University of Toronto Press 2012)

⁶⁷ We explore their behaviour – especially insofar as it relates to the different interests of rural and urban municipalities – in report section 5.1. on Representing Toronto's District Interests to the Ontario Provincial Government.

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

